

AQUASERV

Research services
for **sustainable aquaculture,**
fisheries and **blue economy**

Advisory Boards

Establishment of External Scientific
and Technical (STAB) and Ethics
(EtAB) Advisory Board

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Establishment of External Scientific and Technical (STAB) and Ethics (EtAB) Advisory Board

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Quality Check Review

Reviewer (s)	Main changes / Actions

List of abbreviations and definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
CA	Consortium Agreement
TA	Transnational Access
VA	Virtual Access
WP	Work Package
EXCom	Executive Committee
GA	General Assembly
STAB	Scientific and Technical Advisory Board
EtAB	Ethics Advisory Board

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Relation to Other Project Documents (Deliverables)

If there is a discrepancy between documents, the Grant Agreement, its Annexes and the Consortium Agreement, with possible addenda, take precedence.

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1. Executive Summary

AQUASERV is a research infrastructure project that provides transnational (on-site or remote) and virtual access and training to further scientific advancement and promote, contribute to, and facilitate the implementation of European policies and Missions related to Fisheries, Aquaculture, and the Blue Economy. The deliverable describes the composition of the Scientific and Technical Advisory Board (STAB) and the Ethics Advisory Board (EtAB) approved by the General Assembly.

2. Background / Introduction

AQUASERV is a HORIZON-RIA action under call HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SERV-01 conceived to further scientific advance and promote, contribute, and facilitate the implementation of the European Common Fisheries Policy, the Farm to Fork Strategy, the Sustainable Blue Economy, the European Green Deal and EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030" through the provision of transnational (on-site or remote) and/or virtual access from a catalogue of customised services combining workflows of multiple services from multiple RIs, as well as training, and with an ambitious outreach programme and engagement plan directed at research communities from the public and private sector, including from Ukraine. Although with a wide membership and expertise, the consortium decided to implement external advisory boards (a) Scientific and Technical (STAB) and (b) Ethics (EtAB), whose role is to advise the Executive Committee on key aspects related to the project performance.

The STAB will primarily identify gaps and shortcomings in the AQUASERV service offer, advise on including additional key services to meet the objectives and assist the executive committee in deciding on proposals for service customisation to be supported (based on internal calls).

The EtAB will revise the Ethical Guidelines produced by the coordinator and review flagged TA projects as required on ethical issues.

3. Description of Work

The Executive Committee received proposals for the advisory board members based, as appropriate, on their knowledge and experience with research infrastructures, their expertise related to the topics covered by AQUASERV, including aquaculture, fisheries, aquatic ecology and the blue economy, and ethical aspects relevant to the project (e.g., animal experimentation, access and benefit sharing). The General Assembly approved the advisory board composition through an electronic vote on 13/7/2024.

The advisory board members and their short profiles are as follows:

4. Results and Conclusions

4.1. STAB members

Alex David Rogers, Professor and Director of Science, REV Ocean; Senior Research Fellow, Somerville College, Oxford; Visiting Professor, Dept. of Zoology, University of Oxford.

Ecologist who investigates what structures biodiversity in marine ecosystems. Special interests in the deep sea, particularly seamounts, cold-water corals, chemosynthetic ecosystems, and shallow water and mesophotic tropical coral reef ecosystems.

<https://is.gd/YWz9Ms>

Jeanette Hammer Andersen, Professor at The Arctic University of Norway (UiT) heading the natural products platform Marbio and CEO of KinSea biotechnology start-up company developing marine bioactive compounds into pharmaceutically active products.

<https://en.uit.no/ansatte/jeanette.andersen>

Leonidas Papaharis, Member of the Hellenic Aquaculture Producers Organization Technical Committee and Director of Quality Assurance and Sustainability at Avramar Aquaculture S.A.

<https://is.gd/5lmYjK>

Sebastian Villasante, Professor of Economics and Director of the EqualSea Lab at the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain), ERC project, funded by the European Research Council Consolidator Grant; Distinguished Oportunius Researcher Xunta de Galicia, Researcher Oportunius Program of the Xunta de Galicia, and Karl-Göran Mäler Scholar at the Beijer Institute of Ecological Economics. Conducts interdisciplinary scientific work on the role of values, institutions and knowledge in catalyzing pathways for transformative change in the oceans and people's diets. He is the Coordinating Lead Author of the IPBES Global Transformative Change Assessment, Co-Chair of the PECS Program on Ocean Equity for Sustainable Futures, and co-author of the Global Points of No Return Report.

https://cretus.usc.es/sebastian_villasante/

Jan Pawłowski, Associate Professor at the Department of Genetics and Evolution, University of Geneva and Marine Ecology Department, Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences. Research on the genetic diversity of foraminifera and other groups of eukaryotes to better understand their evolution and help use them as bio-indicators of past and present environmental changes.

<http://www.iopan.gda.pl/Paleo/JanP.html>

4.2. EtAB members

Felicity Huntingford, Emeritus Professor at the University of Glasgow and a fellow of the Royal Society of Edinburgh. Research interests include aggression in fish and welfare. She has been an advisor on the ethics of fish experimentation for Aquaexcel projects.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Felicity_Huntingford

Amber Scholz, Head of Science Policy & Internationalization Department at the Leibniz-Institut DSMZ German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures. Experienced at international science policy and biological research management, including the Access and Benefit Sharing framework.

<https://is.gd/2KPivc>